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A REVIEW: SOLID DISPERSION

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ABSTRACT

Solid dispersions have attracted considerable interest as an efficient means of improving the dissolution rate and hence the bioavailability of a range of poorly water-soluble drugs. Solid dispersions of poorly water-soluble drugs with water-soluble carriers has reduced the incidence of these problems and enhanced dissolution. Solid dispersion technique can be used to enhance the solubility; dissolution rate and absorption of several insoluble drugs. There are various methods available to improve the solubility of the new drug in which solid dispersion emerged promising. A Solid dispersion generally composed of two components- the drug and the polymer matrix. Numerous methods are existing to prepare the solid dispersions. Some of the practical aspects to be considered for the preparation of solid dispersion, such as selection of carrier and method of physicochemical characterization along with an insight into the molecular arrangement of drugs in solid dispersions are also discussed. Finally, an in-depth rationale for limited commercialization of solid dispersion and recent revival has been considered. Solubility is one of the important parameters to achieve desired concentration of drug in systemic circulation for pharmacological response to be shown. Poorly water soluble drugs often require high doses in order to reach therapeutic plasma concentrations after oral administration. Low aqueous solubility is the major problem encountered with formulation development of new chemical entities.

KEY WORDS: Solid dispersion, Solubility, Dissolution rate, Bioavailability, Carrier.

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INTRODUCTION

The oral route of drug administration is the most common and preferred method of delivery due to convenience and ease of ingestion. From a patient's perspective, swallowing a dosage form is a comfortable and a familiar means of taking medication. As a result, patient compliance and hence drug treatment is typically more effective with orally administered medications as compared with other routes of administration [1]. Low aqueous solubility is the major problem encountered with formulation development of new chemical entities. Any drug to be absorbed must be present in the form of an aqueous solution at the site of absorption. Water is the solvent of choice for liquid pharmaceutical formulations. Most of drugs weakly acidic and weakly basic with poor aqueous solubility. Hence, various techniques are used for the improvement of the solubility of poorly water soluble drugs include micronization, chemical modification, pH adjustment, solid dispersion, complexation, co-solvency, micellar solubilization, hydrotrophy etc., [2]. The oral bioavailability depends on several factors including aqueous solubility, drug permeability, dissolution rate, first-pass metabolism, presystemic metabolism, and susceptibility to efflux mechanisms. The most frequent causes of low oral bioavailability are attributed to poor solubility and low permeability [3]. There are various techniques such as, Particle size reduction, micronization, physical modifications, nano-suspension, modification of crystal habit such as, polymorphs, pseudo polymorphs, complexation, solubilization, salt formation, and use of cyclodextrins which can enhance the solubility & dissolution rate of insoluble drug. but this techniques having some practical limitations, solid dispersion technique overcome this practical limitations. However, the major challenge with the design of oral dosage forms lies with their poor bioavailability. Solid dispersion technique can be used to enhance the solubility; dissolution rate and absorption of several insoluble drugs [4]. The term solid dispersion refers to group of solid products consisting of at least two different components, generally a hydrophilic matrix and hydrophobic drugs [5]. The mechanism by which the solubility and dissolution rate of the drug is augmented includes: the particle size of the drug is abridged to submicron size or to the molecular size in the case where solid solution is achieved. The particle size reduction usually enhances the rate of dissolution; the changed from crystalline to amorphous form, the high energetic state which is very soluble; finally the wettability of the drug particle is enhanced by the dissolution carrier. Regardless of these promising advantages, the application of solid dispersion in pharmaceutical industry has certain boundarie.

Table 1: BCS classification system [6]

Class	Solubility	Permeability	Example of Drugs
Class I	High solubility	High permeability	Benzapril, Loxoprofen, Sumatriptan etc.
Class II	High solubility	Low permeability	Valsartan, Nimesulide, Loratadine, Aceclofenac, Glimepiride etc
Class III	Low solubility	High permeability	Gabapentine, Topiramate, Atropine etc.
Class IV	Low solubility	Low permeability	Hydrochlorthiazide, Furosemide, Meloxicam etc.

Table 2: Materials used as carrier for solid dispersion [7]

S. N.	Materials Used As Carriers	Examples
1.	Sugars	Dextrose, sucrose, galactose, sorbitol, maltose, xylitol mannitol, lactose
2.	Acids	Citric acid, succinic acid
3.	Polymeric materials	Povidone (PVP), polyethylene glycol (PEG), hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose, hydroxy ethyl cellulose, cyclodextrin, hydroxy propyl cellulose, pectin, galactomannan
4.	Insoluble or enteric polymer	HPMC phthalate, eudragit L100, eudragit S100, Eudragit RL, Eudragit RS
5.	Surfactants	Polyoxyethylene stearate, renex, poloxamer 188, texafor AIP, deoxycholic acid, tweens, spans
6.	Miscellaneous	Pentaerythritol, pentaerythrityl tetraacetate, urea, urethane, hydroxy alkyl xanthins

Drug absorption from the gastrointestinal (GI) tract can be limited by a variety of factors with the most significant contributors being poor aqueous solubility and/or poor membrane permeability of the drug molecule. When delivering an active agent orally, it must first dissolve in gastric and/or intestinal fluids before it can then permeate the membranes of the GI tract to reach systemic circulation. Therefore, a drug with poor aqueous solubility will typically exhibit dissolution rate limited absorption, and a drug with poor membrane permeability will typically

exhibit permeation rate limited absorption. Hence, two areas of pharmaceutical research that focus on improving the oral bioavailability of active agents include enhancing solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water-soluble drugs and enhancing permeability of poorly permeable drugs. This article focuses on the former, in particular, the use of solid dispersion technologies to improve the dissolution characteristics of poorly water-soluble drugs and in turn their oral bioavailability. Numerous solid dispersion systems have been demonstrated in the pharmaceutical literature to improve the dissolution properties of poorly water-soluble drugs [8]. One such formulation approach that has been shown to significantly enhance absorption of such drugs is to formulate solid dispersion. The term solid dispersion refers to a group of solid products consisting of at least two different components, generally a hydrophilic matrix and a hydrophobic drug. The matrix can be either crystalline or amorphous. When the solid dispersion is exposed to aqueous media, the carrier dissolves and the drug releases as fine colloidal particles. The resulting enhanced surface area produces higher dissolution rate and enhances bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs. In addition, in solid dispersions, a portion of drug dissolves immediately to saturate the gastrointestinal tract fluid, and excess drug precipitates as fine colloidal particles or oily globules of submicron size [9]. The advantage of solid dispersions over conventional tablet or capsule is shown schematically in Figure 1.

Types of Solid Dispersions:

Eutectic mixtures:

A simple eutectic mixture consists of two compounds which are completely miscible in the liquid state but only to a very limited extent in the solid state. It is prepared by rapid solidification of fused melt of two components that show complete liquid miscibility but negligible solid-solid solution [10-13]

Amorphous precipitation in crystalline matrix:

This is similar to simple eutectic mixtures but only difference is that drug is precipitated out in an amorphous form [14-15].

Solid solution: Solid solutions are comparable to liquid solutions, consisting of just one phase irrespective of the number of components. In the case of solid solutions, the drug's particle size has been reduced to its absolute minimum viz. the molecular dimensions [16] and the dissolution rate is determined by the dissolution rate of the carrier. Classified according to their miscibility

(continuous versus discontinuous solid solutions) or second, according to the way in which the solvate molecules are distributed in the solventum (substitutional, interstitial or amorphous).

Continuous solid solutions:

In a continuous solid solution, the components are miscible in all proportions. Theoretically, this means that the bonding strength between the two components is stronger than the bonding strength between the molecules of each of the individual components. Solid solutions of this type have not been reported in the pharmaceutical world till date.

Discontinuous solid solutions:

In the case of discontinuous solid solutions, the solubility of each of the components in the other component is limited. Due to practical considerations it has been suggested by Goldberg et al. [17] that the term 'solid solution' should only be applied when the mutual solubility of the two components exceeds 5%.

Substitutional solid dispersions:

Substitution is only possible when the size of the solute molecules differs by less than 15% or so from that of the solvent molecules [18]. Classical solid solutions have crystalline structure, in which the solute molecules can either substitute for solvent molecules in the crystal lattice or fit into the intrsticies between the solvent molecule.

Interstitial solid solutions:

In interstitial solid solutions, the dissolved molecules occupy the interstitial spaces between the solvent molecules in the crystal lattice. Solute molecule diameter should be less than 0.59 times than that of solvent molecular diameter [16].

Glass solution and suspensions:

Glass solutions are homogeneous glassy system in which solute dissolves in glass carrier. Glass suspensions are mixture in which precipitated particles are suspended in glass solvent. Lattice energy is much lower in glass solution and suspension [13].

Fig. 2: Phase diagram for eutectic system (Mura P. et al., 1996)

Fig. 3: Phase diagram for a discontinuous solid solution

Fig. 4: Substitutional crystalline solid

Fig. 5: Interstitial crystalline solid solution solution

Selection of a Carrier:

A carrier should meet the following criteria to be suitable for increasing the dissolution rate of a drug [19,20, 21, 22].

- ❖ Freely water-soluble with intrinsic rapid dissolution properties.
- ❖ Non-toxic and pharmacologically inert.
- ❖ Heat stable with a low melting point for the melt method.
- ❖ Soluble in a variety of solvents and pass through a vitreous state upon solvent evaporation for the solvent method.
- ❖ Able to preferably increase the aqueous solubility of the drug.
- ❖ Chemically compatible with the drug and not form a strongly bonded complex with the drug.

First Generation Carriers:

Example: Crystalline carriers: Urea, Sugars, Organic acids [23].

Second Generation Carriers:

Example: Fully synthetic polymers include povidone (PVP), polyethyleneglycols (PEG) and polymethacrylates [22]. Natural product based polymers are mainly composed by cellulose derivatives, such as hydroxypropylmethylcellulose (HPMC), ethylcellulose or hydroxypropylcellulose or starch derivatives, like cyclodextrins [24].

Third Generation Carriers:

Example: Surface active self-emulsifying carriers: Poloxamer 408, Tween 80, and Gelucire 44/141

Classification of Solid Dispersion

Table 3: Types of Solid Dispersion [18]

S.No	Solid Dispersion Type	Matrix*	Drug**	Remarks No	phases	Reference
1.	Eutectics	C	C	The first type of solid dispersion Prepared	2	(Chiou and Riegelman, 1971)
2.	Amorphous precipitations in crystalline matrix	C	A	Rarely Encountered	2	(Breitenbach AH, 2002); (Mullins and Macek, 1960)
3.	Solid solutions					
A.	Continuous Solid Solutions	C	M	Miscible at all composition, never prepared	1	(Goldberg <i>et al.</i> , 1965]
B	Discontinuous solid solutions	C	M	Partially miscible, 2 phases even though drug is molecularly dispersed	2	Sekiguchi K and Obi N (1961)

C	Substitutional solid solutions	C	M	Molecular diameter of drug (solute) differs less than 5% from the matrix (solvent) diameter. In that case the drug and matrix are substitutional. Can be continuous or discontinuous. When discontinuous: 2 phases even though drug is molecularly dispersed	1 or 2	(Rastogi and Verma, 1956); (Wilcox <i>et al.</i> , 1964)
D	Interstitial solid solutions	C	M	Drug (solute) molecular diameter less than 59% of matrix (solvent) diameter. Usually limited miscibility, discontinuous.	2	(Chiou and Riegelman, 1971); (Chiou and Riegelman, 1969)
4.	Glass suspension	A	C	Particle size of dispersed phase dependent on cooling/evaporation rate. Obtained after crystallization of drug in amorphous matrix	2	Riegelman, 1971); (Sarkari M <i>et al.</i> , 2002)
5.	Glass suspension	A	A	Particle size of dispersed phase dependent on cooling/evaporation rate many solid dispersions are of this type	2	Riegelman, 1971); (Sarkari M <i>et al.</i> , 2002)
6.	Glass solution	A	M	Requires miscibility OR solid solubility, complex formation or upon fast cooling OR evaporation during preparation, many (recent) examples especially with PVP	1	Simonelli AP <i>et al.</i> , 1969

A: matrix in the amorphous state, C: matrix in the crystalline state **: A: drug dispersed as amorphous clusters in the matrix, C: drug dispersed as crystalline particles in the matrix, M: drug molecularly dispersed throughout the matrix

1. Fusion / Melting method
2. Solvent method
3. Melting solvent method (melt evaporation)
4. Melt extrusion methods
5. Lyophilization techniques
6. Melt agglomeration Process
7. The use of surfactant
8. Electrospinning
9. Super Critical Fluid (Scf) technology

1. Fusion method

The melting or fusion method is the preparation of physical mixture of a drug and a water-soluble carrier and heating it directly until it melts. The melted mixture is then solidified rapidly in an ice-bath under vigorous stirring. The final solid mass is crushed, pulverized and sieved.

Appropriately this has undergone many modifications in pouring the homogenous melt in the form of a thin layer onto a ferrite plate or a stainless steel plate and cooled by flowing air or water on the opposite side of the plate. In addition, a super-saturation of a solute or drug in a system can often be obtained by quenching the melt rapidly from a high temperature. Under such conditions, the solute molecule is arrested in the solvent matrix by the instantaneous solidification process. The quenching technique gives a much finer dispersion of crystallites when used for simple eutectic mixtures. However many substances, either drugs or carriers, may decompose during the fusion process which employs high temperature. It may also cause evaporation of volatile drug or volatile carrier during the fusion process at high temperature. Some of the means to overcome these problems could be heating the physical mixture in a sealed container or melting it under vacuum or in presence of inert gas like nitrogen to prevent oxidative degradation of drug or carrier.

The main advantages of this method are its simplicity and economy. The disadvantages are: i) that the method is only applied when the drug and matrix are compatible and when they mix well at the heating temperature. When the drug and matrix are incompatible two liquid phases or suspension can be observed in the heated mixture which results in an inhomogeneous solid

dispersion and this problem can be prevented by using surfactants. ii) Another problem may arise during cooling when the drug-matrix miscibility changes. In this case phase separation can occur. Indeed, it was observed that when the mixture was slowly cooled, crystalline drug occurred, whereas fast cooling yielded amorphous solid dispersions. iii) Many substances, either drugs or carriers, may decompose during the fusion process at high temperatures [5, 21].

2. Solvent Method

The first step in the solvent method is the preparation of a solution containing both matrix material and drug. The second step involves the removal of solvent(s) resulting in formation of a solid dispersion. Mixing at the molecular level is preferred, because this leads to optimal dissolution properties. The main advantage of the solvent method is thermal decomposition of drugs or carriers can be prevented because of the relatively low temperatures required for the evaporation of organic solvents. However, using the solvent method the pharmaceutical engineer faces two challenges. The first challenge is to mix both drug and matrix in one solution, which is difficult when they differ significantly in polarity. To minimize the drug particle size in the solid dispersion, the drug and matrix have to be dispersed in the solvent as fine as possible, preferably drug and matrix material are in the dissolved state in one solution. Low drug concentrations are used to dissolve both drug and matrix material in water, but this requires evaporation of tremendous amounts of solvent, making the process expensive and impractical. Solubilizers like cyclodextrins or surfactants like Tween80® increase the aqueous solubility of the drug substantially. However, the amounts of solubilizers or surfactants in the final product are often eminent. Moreover, only dosage forms with low drug loads are possible. In addition, they are not always tolerated well in the body or may even be toxic. The second challenge in the solvent method is to prevent phase separation, e.g. crystallization of either drug or matrix, during removal of the solvent(s). Drying at hightemperatures speeds up the process and reduces the time available for phase separation. On the other hand, at high temperatures the molecular mobility of drug and matrix remains high, favoring phase separation (e.g., crystallization). To dry the solutions, vacuum drying moderate heating is often used. Sometimes, the solvent evaporation is accelerated by using a rotary evaporator. Afterwards the formed solid dispersion is often stored in vacuum desiccators to remove the residual solvent. Another drying technique is spray drying.

For these reasons, hot melt extrusion is the current method of choice for the preparation of solid dispersions [5,22,23]

3. Melting solvent method (melt evaporation)

It involves preparation of solid dispersions by dissolving the drug in a suitable liquid solvent and then incorporating the solution directly into the melt of polyethylene glycol, which is then evaporated until a clear, solvent free film is left. The film is further dried to constant weight. The 5 –10% (w/w) of liquid compounds can be incorporated into polyethylene glycol 6000 without significant loss of its solid property. Also the liquid solvent used may affect the polymorphic form of the drug, which precipitates as the solid dispersion. This technique possesses unique advantages of both the fusion and solvent evaporation methods. From a practical standpoint, it is only limited to drugs with a low therapeutic dose e.g. below 50 mg and particularly useful for drugs that are thermolabile or have high melting points [5, 24].

4. Melt extrusion method

Hot-stage extrusion (HME) consists of the extrusion, at high rotational speed, of the drug and carrier, previously mixed, at melting temperature for a small period of time. Solid dispersion by this method is composed of active ingredient and carrier, and prepared by hot-stage extrusion using a co-rotating twin-screw extruder. The drug/carrier mix is simultaneously melted, homogenized and then extruded and shaped as tablets, granules, pellets, sheets, sticks or powder. The intermediates can then be further processed into conventional tablets. An important advantage of the hot melt extrusion method is that the drug/carrier mix is only subjected to an elevated temperature for about 1min, which enables drugs that are somewhat thermolabile to be processed. The concentration of drug in the dispersions is always 40% (w/w). Samples are milled for 1 min with a cutting mill and sieved to exclude particles >355 μ . A reduction in processing temperature can be achieved by the association of hot-stage extrusion with the use of carbon dioxide as a plasticizer which broadens the application of hot-stage extrusion to thermally labile compounds. HME also offers several advantages over traditional pharmaceutical processing techniques including the absence of solvents, few processing steps, continuous operation, and low temperature, short residence time which prevents the drug-carrier mixture from thermal degradation, more possibility of the formation of solid dispersions and improved bioavailability.

This method has several disadvantages these are: (i) high shear forces may produce high local temperature in the extruder therefore it may create a problem for heat sensitive materials, (ii) just like traditional fusion method, miscibility of drug and carrier matrix can be a problem. Some examples of pharmaceutically approved polymeric materials which are used in hot-melt extrusion include vinyl polymers [polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), PVP-vinyl acetate (PVP-VA)], polyethylene oxide (PEO), Eudragit® (acrylates), Polyethylene glycol (PEG) and cellulose derivatives.

5. Lyophilization Technique (Freeze-drying)

Lyophilization has been thought of a molecular mixing technique where the drug and carrier are co dissolved in a common solvent, frozen and sublimed to obtain a lyophilized molecular dispersion. This technique was proposed as an alternative technique to solvent evaporation.

The advantages of freeze drying is that the drug is subjected to minimal thermal stress during the formation of the solid dispersion and the risk of phase separation is minimized as soon as the solution is vitrified. An even more promising drying technique is spray-freeze drying. The solvent is sprayed into liquid nitrogen or cold dry air and the frozen droplets are subsequently lyophilized. The large surface area and direct contact with the cooling agent results in even faster vitrification, thereby decreasing the risk for phase separation to a minimum. Moreover, spray freeze drying offers the potential to customize the size of the particle to make them suitable for further processing or applications like pulmonary or nasal administration [21, 22, 23].

6. Melt Agglomeration Process

This technique has been used to prepare solid dispersion wherein the binder acts as a carrier. In addition, solid dispersions are prepared either by heating binder, drug and excipient to a temperature above the melting point of the binder (melt- in procedure) or by spraying a dispersion of drug in molten binder on the heated excipient (spray-on procedure) by using a high shear mixer. The rotary processor might be preferable to the high melt agglomeration because it is easier to control the temperature and because a higher binder content can be incorporated in the agglomerates. The effect of binder type, method of manufacturing and particle size are critical parameters in preparation of solid dispersion by melt agglomeration. It has been found that the melt in procedure gives a higher dissolution rates than the spray-on procedure with PEG

3000, poloxamer 188 and gelucire 50/13 attributed to immersion mechanism of agglomerate formation and growth. In addition the melt in procedure also results in homogenous distribution of drug in agglomerate. Larger particles results in densification of agglomerates while fine particle cause complete adhesion to the mass to bowl shortly after melting attributed to distribution and coalescence of the fine particles [5].

7. The use of surfactant

The utility of the surfactant systems in solubilization is very important. Adsorption of surfactant on solid surface can modify their hydrophobicity, surface charge, and other key properties that govern interfacial processes such as flocculation/dispersion, floating, wetting, solubilization, detergency, and enhanced oil recovery and corrosion inhibition. Surfactants have also been reported to cause solvation/plasticization, manifesting in reduction of melting the active pharmaceutical ingredients, glass transition temperature and the combined glass transition temperature of solid dispersions. Because of these unique properties, surfactants have attracted the attention of investigators for preparation of solid dispersions [5].

8. Electrospinning

Electrospinning is a process in which solid fibers are produced from a polymeric fluid stream solution or melt delivered through a millimeter-scale nozzle. This process involves the application of a strong electrostatic field over a conductive capillary attaching to a reservoir containing a polymer solution or melt and a conductive collection screen. Upon increasing the electrostatic field strength up to but not exceeding a critical value, charge species accumulate on the surface of a pendant drop; destabilize the hemispherical shape into a conical shape (commonly known as Taylor's cone). Beyond the critical value, a charged polymer jet is ejected from the apex of the cone (as a way of relieving the charge built-up on the surface of the pendant drop). The ejected charged jet is then carried to the collection screen via the electrostatic force. The thinning down of the charged jet is limited. If the viscosity increases, the charged jet is dried. This technique has tremendous potential for the preparation of nanofibres and controlling the release of biomedicine, as it is simplest, the cheapest this technique can be utilized for the preparation of solid dispersions in future [5, 21].

9. Super Critical Fluid (Scf) Technology

The supercritical fluid antisolvent techniques, carbon dioxide are used as an antisolvent for the solute but as a solvent with respect to the organic solvent. Different acronyms were used by various authors to denote micronization processes: aerosol solvent extraction system, precipitation with a compressed fluid antisolvent, gas anti-solvent, solution enhanced dispersion by supercritical fluids and supercritical antisolvent. Once the drug particles are solubilised within SCF, they may be recrystallised at greatly reduced particle sizes. The flexibility and precision offered by SCF processes allows micronization of drug particles within narrow ranges of particle size, often to sub-micron levels. Current SCF processes have demonstrated the ability to create nanoparticulate suspensions of particles 5-2,000nm in diameter. The SAS process involves the spraying of the solution composed of the solute and of the organic solvent into a continuous supercritical phase flowing concurrently. Use of supercritical carbon dioxide is advantageous as it is much easier to remove from the polymeric materials when the process is complete, even though a small amount of carbon dioxide remains trapped inside the polymer; it poses no danger to the patient. In addition the ability of carbon dioxide to plasticize and swell polymers can also be exploited and the process can be carried out near room temperature. Moreover, supercritical fluids are used to lower the temperature of melt dispersion process by reducing the melting temperature of dispersed active agent. The low operating conditions (temperature and pressure) make SCFs attractive for pharmaceutical research [5, 21,22, 23].

CONCLUSION

The solid dispersion method is one of the effective approaches to achieve the goal of solubility enhancement of poorly water-soluble drugs. The present study conclusively indicated that the use of various solid dispersion methods by using water soluble carrier improved the solubility of poorly water soluble drug .Solid dispersions over the last few decades indicates that this is a very lucrative approach to improving the release rate and oral bioavailability of hydrophobic drugs. Two trends powerfully favour an increasing role for solid dispersions in pharmaceutical development the growing number of drug candidates which are poorly soluble, and the considerable improvements in the manufacturing techniques for solid dispersions. Solid dispersions to improve the dissolution properties as well as to sustain the drug release .The enhancement of oral bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs remains one of the most

challenging aspects of drug development .These significantly help to improve the bioavailability and bioequivalence

Figure 2: Methods of preparation of solid dispersions

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